

ACTIVITIES OF AMERICAN INSURANCE COMPANIES IN THE TERRITORY OF THE RUSSIAN EMPIRE.

Azizbek Kholiev

candidate of historical sciences, associate Professor,

National University of Uzbekistan,

Uzbekistan, Tashkent

ABSTRACT. The main aspects of the activities of US insurance companies on the territory of the Russian empire in the last quarter of the 19th - early 20th centuries are considered in the presented article from a historical point of view.

KEYWORDS. USA, insurance, companies, Russia, activity, financial relations, companies, capital, policy.

One of the elements of Russia's financial ties with foreign countries, and in particular with the United States, was the activity of American insurance companies on the territory of the Russian Empire.

Under normal conditions, insurance companies have huge free amounts that enter the loan capital market. Insurance capitals have their own sphere of application, and to the extent that their interests collide with the interests of banks, competition between them is possible. From the point of view of the investment process, banks and insurance companies are only different channels of investment, and therefore, in large financial groupings, both banks and insurance companies are usually represented.

Most major insurance companies in the US were not ordinary joint-stock companies, but were organized in the form of so-called "mutual companies". Formally, the "owners" of such companies are equally considered to be all holders

of policies for a certain amount. Accordingly, the income in them is not issued in the form of dividends on shares, but is distributed among the insured as dividends on policies.

Historically, the first and most important form of financing by US insurance companies was their purchase of railroad bonds (in 1906, railroad bonds accounted for 34% of their assets) [1, p.82]. Railways and insurance companies acted at that time as complementary links in the formation of the structure of financial capital.

A characteristic feature of the insurance business in the United States was its enormous degree of concentration. In the field of life insurance, it turned out to be even higher than the concentration of banks. In the assets of all US financial institutions, the share of insurance companies in 1900 was 12% [2, p.267].

The central factor in the development of the insurance business in the last quarter of the nineteenth century there was a continuous unrestricted growth, as a result of which a group of approximately equal in strength and dominating only together companies was formed – the «Big Three» oligopoly («Mutual Life Insurance C^o», «New York Life Insurance C^o» и «Equitable Life Insurance C^o») and several lagging behind them «The Prudential C^o» and «Metropolitan Life Insurance C^o» [5, p.12]. Until 1886, «Mutual» retained the championship, then «Equitable» took the palm, in 1899 losing it to «New York».

The structure of all five largest companies was the same: the board - the general agency abroad - regional agencies - insurance agents who worked on commission from sold policies. The leading trend in the internal development of insurance companies was their bureaucratization, combined with a clear concentration of power at the highest level of the administrative hierarchy - especially between 1890 and 1900.

Each company from the “five” crossed the threshold of \$ 1 billion in insurance premiums by 1899; at the same time, it took New York 54 years to get the first billion, and the milestone of \$ 2 billion was passed in just 6 years. In 1902, the total

investment in policies of the three largest companies was equal to the total amount of cash circulating in the USA, and by 1909, 40% of adult Americans were insurance policy holders [5, p.145].

The emergence of American insurance companies abroad dates back to before the Civil War of 1861-1865. Initially, these were companies that did not belong to the “five”. However, American companies really took it seriously between 1885 and 1905. By 1900, “Equitable” operated in almost 100 states and territories, “New York” in almost 50, “Mutual” in 20. The total income of the three companies from operations abroad by 1905 was equivalent to about 1/8 of the amount of industrial exports of the United States of America.

American insurance companies abroad constantly met the requirements of local governments to form mandatory insurance reserves. In Western Europe, American insurance companies were quite active in investing in loans that seemed promising and on their own initiative. In Russia, their investment activity did not go beyond the strict necessity, that is, it was part of the organization of the very process of functioning, and not a conscious investment program. The activities of American insurance companies abroad were generally less bound by local competition than by government restrictions. American companies abroad kept a close eye on each other.

As for the early stage of the activities of American insurance companies in Russia, it most likely dates back to the 70s of the 19th century. According to G.P. Kuropyatnik, already at that time the Americans began to make efforts to take the insurance business in Russia into their own hands. The “backlog” of the 1870s in the organization of insurance societies later served as a springboard for a significant crowding out of Russian capital, as well as foreign capital in this extremely profitable area. New York companies «Life Saving Society» and «New York Life Insurance C^o» were at the forefront of the American introduction into the Russian insurance business [3, p.67].

The «New York» Society received formal permission from the Russian authorities in 1885, and the «Equitable» Society in 1890 [4, p.30]

Both companies began by violating the laws of the country by underhand issuing policies before the government officially approved policy terms and in defiance of the 1887 rules for accounting and control of the reserve fund.

The appearance of alarming reports of major scams involving American insurance companies both in America itself and in Europe caused rather stringent conditions for allowing American insurance companies to operate in Russia. The “final” conditions for the activities of American insurance companies provided for three types of guarantees: depositing a pledge of 500 thousand rubles for each company with the State Bank, the formation of a reserve fund in the form of a package of bonds deposited with the State Bank, sufficient to cover 30% of the amounts of all policies in Russia, and insurance capital formed for additional security of operations from deductions of 10% of profit.

The list of permitted transactions included insurance in case of death or for a certain period, dowry insurance for children, and life or temporary annuity insurance [2, p.271].

The period from the late 1880s until 1914 was a time of systematic growth of the Russian branches of both societies. Compared to “Equitable”, “New York” had almost twice the volume of operations, a denser network of representative offices and a wider range of servicing banks. Russia quickly occupied the second most important place among the foreign branches of the “New York” Society. By 1913, the company's operations were second only to the “Rossiya” insurance company in terms of its scope. There is evidence that American companies practiced concluding reinsurance contracts with Russian insurance companies.

Despite the large scope of their operations, American insurance companies have not become a major force either in the Russian insurance (controlling a little

more than 34%), or in the Russian stock market. All free funds were mainly exported by them from Russia and invested directly in the USA or Canada themselves.

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